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Better healthcare

H63D Syndrome Type-1: Beyond Hemochromatosis and Towards a Comprehensive Understanding of Metal Accumulation Diseases

Abstract

H63D Syndrome is a genetic disorder characterized by iron accumulation in the body, which has been historically associated with hereditary hemochromatosis (HH). However, recent research has provided evidence that this syndrome, particularly type-1 H63D, has less in common with HH than with other metal accumulation diseases such as Wilson's Disease. This paper aims to elucidate the distinct features of H63D Syndrome, emphasizing the differences between H63D and HH, as well as the unique challenges associated with its treatment. Furthermore, we will explore the role of non-transferrin-bound iron (NTBI) in the pathophysiology of H63D Syndrome and its implications on cellular function and heart health.

H63D Syndrome type-1 is closer related to Wilson's Disease than to Hereditary Hemochromatosis

Hereditary hemochromatosis (HH) is a well-known genetic disorder characterized by excessive iron absorption and

accumulation in the body, leading organ dysfunction and destruction (Pietrangelo, 2010). The H63D mutation, located on the HFE gene, has been previously linked to HH (Feder et al., 1996). However, recent studies have challenged this association, suggesting that H63D Syndrome, especially type-1, bears a closer resemblance to other

metal accumulation diseases such as Wilson's Disease (WD) (Schilsky, 2019). The H63D mutation results in a substitution of aspartic acid for histidine at position 63 in the HFE protein (Feder et al., 1996). This mutation impairs the ability of the HFE protein to regulate iron absorption and transportation, leading to increased iron deposition in tissues (Barton et al., 1998). However, unlike HH, H63D Syndrome is predominantly characterized by the presence of non-transferrin-bound iron (NTBI) rather than excessive ferritin levels (Brissot et al., 2012). This key difference has significant implications on the disease's clinical presentation, pathophysiology, and treatment options.

Wilson's Disease is an autosomal recessive disorder caused by mutations in the *ATP7B* gene, leading to copper accumulation in tissues, particularly in the liver and brain (Bandmann et al., 2015). Although H63D Syndrome and WD differ in the primary metal involved, both disorders share a number of symptoms, especially including hepatomegaly, liver damages, heart failure, and neurological manifestations (Schilsky, 2019).

While Wilson's Disease is caused by copper, in H63D syndrome NTBI is the culprit. NTBI is formed in an exponential function inside the body of circulating free (basal) iron that is not bound to the iron-transport protein transferrin as soon as transferrin saturation exceeds 50% (Brissot et al., 2012). In H63D Syndrome, increased levels of NTBI can cause damage to parenchymal cells, disrupting the function of sodium, calcium, and potassium channels and posing a risk to heart health (Grootveld & Bell, 2020). The presence of NTBI contributes to the distinct clinical picture of H63D Syndrome compared to classic HH, and provides a rationale for the exploration of alternative treatment options.

Chelation therapy and phlebotomy are well-established treatment options for HH, aimed at reducing iron overload and its associated complications (Barton et al., 1998). However, in H63D Syndrome, these treatments are not suitable as long as ferritin levels remain within the low-normal range (Brissot et al., 2012). This is because the primary issue in H63D Syndrome is the presence of NTBI, which is not effectively addressed by both, either chelation and classic phlebotomy. The ineffectiveness of these treatments can be attributed to the fact that they target iron bound to transferrin or stored as ferritin, rather than the unbound, toxic NTBI (Grootveld & Bell, 2020). If the ferritin level is low while there is an NTBI overload at the same time, a chelation or excessive phlebotomies therapy might even end with a dead patient.

Therefore, there is a need for alternative therapeutic approaches that specifically target NTBI in H63D Syndrome. Research on the development of novel drugs aimed at reducing NTBI levels is currently underway, with a focus on iron-binding molecules and iron mobilizing agents (Grootveld & Bell, 2020). Future studies should also investigate the potential of gene therapy and other targeted treatments to address the unique challenges presented by H63D Syndrome.

Knowledge is currently the most important weapon to treat H63D Syndrome patients as good as possible. Every medical professional should know that H63D Syndrome is a distinct genetic disorder that shares similarities with other metal accumulation diseases such as Wilson's Disease. The presence of NTBI, rather than excessive ferritin levels, differentiates H63D Syndrome from classic hereditary hemochromatosis and poses unique challenges in terms of treatment. A deeper

understanding of the pathophysiology of H63D Syndrome, and the development of novel therapeutic approaches targeting NTBI, are essential to improving the management and prognosis of this complex disorder. As we continue to refine our understanding of H63D Syndrome, it is essential to consider the clinical implications of the differences between this condition and hereditary hemochromatosis. Accurate diagnosis and differentiation of these disorders are crucial for the implementation of appropriate treatment strategies and improved patient outcomes.

Current diagnostic methods for H63D Syndrome may include genetic testing, evaluation of serum iron markers (especially transferrin saturation TFsat), and assessment of liver and heart function (Pietrangelo, 2010). However, considering the role of NTBI in the pathophysiology of H63D Syndrome, there is a need for the development of more precise diagnostic tools that specifically target this form of circulating iron. The utilization of NTBI-specific biomarkers may provide a more accurate representation of disease severity and progression, allowing for tailored treatment plans and better patient management.

Increased awareness of H63D Syndrome among healthcare professionals is vital for the early identification and management of patients with this condition. Ensuring that physicians, nurses, and other healthcare providers are educated on the unique features of H63D Syndrome, its similarities with Wilson's Disease, and the limitations of traditional treatments such as chelation and phlebotomy, can contribute to improved patient care. Moreover, patient education is of utmost importance. Individuals diagnosed with H63D Syndrome should be provided with comprehensive information on their

condition, potential complications, and the rationale behind their treatment plan. This may facilitate adherence to medical recommendations and improve overall health outcomes.

The interplay between genetic factors and environmental influences has long been recognized as a determinant of disease development and progression. In the context of H63D Syndrome, understanding the potential impact of environmental factors and lifestyle choices on disease manifestation is crucial for devising preventive measures and enhancing patient care.

Dietary iron intake may play a role in exacerbating or mitigating the symptoms of H63D Syndrome. A diet high in iron-rich foods, such as red meat, organ meats, and certain legumes, may contribute to increased NTBI levels (TFsat >50%) and thus worsen the clinical manifestations of H63D Syndrome (Grootveld & Bell, 2020). Conversely, a diet low in iron, with an emphasis on plant-based foods (eaten with a calcium drink, black tea or alcohol free wine, tannins) and limited consumption of heme iron sources, may help reduce NTBI levels and alleviate symptoms (Barton et al., 1998). Moreover, certain dietary factors may influence iron absorption. For instance, the consumption of foods rich in vitamin C, such as citrus fruits, can enhance iron absorption, while calcium and polyphenols can inhibit it (Hallberg & Hulthén, 2000). A tailored dietary plan that considers these factors may be beneficial for individuals with H63D Syndrome.

Alcohol consumption has been associated with increased iron absorption and may exacerbate iron overload in patients with H63D Syndrome (Borgna-Pignatti & Garani, 2008). Therefore, it is advisable for individuals with this condition to limit

alcohol intake, or - in severe cases - abstain altogether, to minimize the risk of disease progression and complications. Regular physical activity has been suggested to positively affect iron metabolism and reduce the risk of iron overload (Sim et al., 2019). Engaging in regular exercise may contribute to a better quality of life for patients with H63D Syndrome by promoting overall health and potentially mitigating the effects of iron accumulation. A comprehensive understanding of H63D Syndrome requires considering the role of environmental factors and lifestyle choices in disease progression. By adopting tailored dietary plans, reducing alcohol intake, and engaging in regular physical activity, individuals with H63D Syndrome may be able to better manage their condition and improve their overall health. As we continue to refine our understanding of H63D Syndrome, it is essential to consider the clinical implications of the differences between this condition and hereditary hemochromatosis. Accurate diagnosis and differentiation of these disorders are crucial for the implementation of appropriate treatment strategies and improved patient outcomes.

Outlook

Current diagnostic methods for H63D Syndrome may include genetic testing, evaluation of serum iron markers, and assessment of liver function (Pietrangelo, 2010). However, considering the unique role of NTBI in the pathophysiology of H63D Syndrome, there is a need for the development of more precise diagnostic tools that specifically target this form of circulating iron. As mentioned earlier, the utilization of NTBI-specific biomarkers might hopefully provide a more accurate representation of disease severity and progression, allowing for tailored treatment plans and better patient management.

Increased awareness of H63D Syndrome among healthcare professionals is vital for the early identification and management of patients with this condition. Ensuring that physicians, nurses, and other healthcare providers are educated on the unique features of H63D Syndrome, its similarities with Wilson's Disease, and the limitations of traditional treatments such as chelation and phlebotomy, can contribute to improved patient care. Moreover, patient education is of utmost importance. Individuals diagnosed with H63D Syndrome should be provided with comprehensive information on their condition, potential complications, and the rationale behind their treatment plan. This may facilitate adherence to medical recommendations and improve overall health outcomes.

Conclusion

In summary, H63D Syndrome represents a very unique genetic disorder that requires a profound understanding of its somewhat complex pathophysiology, similarities with other metal accumulation diseases, and treatment options. Future research should focus on the development of novel therapeutic approaches targeting NTBI, as well as the refinement of diagnostic tools and strategies for patient management. By enhancing our knowledge of H63D Syndrome and addressing the challenges it presents, we can ultimately improve the lives of those affected by this complex condition.

Acknowledgments

Swabian Research would like to thank Mr. Riku Honda of Tokyo (Japan) for funding this work.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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